

Why Do Anti-sectarian Protesters Vote for Sectarian Parties?

Simon Mabon

*Simon Mabon is Chair in International Politics at Lancaster University where he directs [SEPAD](#). He is the author of *The Struggle for Supremacy in the Middle East: Saudi Arabia and Iran* (Cambridge University Press, 2023) and *Houses Built on Sand: Violence, Sovereignty and Revolution in the Middle East* (Manchester University Press, 2020). Email: s.mabon@lancaster.ac.uk*

In late 2019, protesters took to the streets of Iraq and Lebanon demanding an end to the domination of political life by sectarian groups. The organization of political life in accordance with identity concerns—enshrined within power sharing systems—has long provoked ire amongst Iraqis and Lebanese, culminating in widespread protests across the final months of 2019. With chants of *kellon yani kellon*—all of them means all of them—and *nurid watan*—we want a homeland—ringing out across urban centers, the ordering principles of political and social life across the two states faced an existential challenge. And yet, in the election that followed, sectarian parties were overwhelmingly returned to power, seemingly at odds with the widespread protests that had taken place in the months and years earlier.

While this choice may be pragmatic given the scale of crises in both states, it remains somewhat surprising given the depth of anger expressed by many in preceding years and broader efforts to engage in processes of desectarianization (Mabon, 2020). In this intervention I reflect on why this took place, drawing on data from a SEPAD/TOI survey conducted in Lebanon and Iraq in 2021. The surveys were designed by a group of scholars from the Sectarianism, Proxies and De-sec

tarianisation (SEPAD) project and Bringing in the Other Islamists (TOI) who work on each state and put in the field by survey companies based in Lebanon and Iraq. The surveys recruited over 2000 respondents from a wide social base. Ultimately the intervention argues that while the protesters point to the wider rejection of sectarian politics, the material capabilities of sectarian parties meant that in times of existential crisis, such parties were deemed to offer support necessary for survival.

Sectarianism and the State in Lebanon and Iraq

Lebanon and Iraq are often heralded as examples par excellence of states shaped by a legacy of sectarian difference (Salloukh, 2020; Salloukh et al, 2015; Dodge, 2018). Sectarian identities are interwoven into the very fabric of political life in both states, much to the chagrin of many. Power sharing modes of political engagement were put in place in Lebanon and Iraq as a means of addressing violent social cleavages. Whilst differing in implementation, the power sharing systems in both states are broadly mapped onto social cleavages, reinforcing those lines of in/exclusion in the process and meaning that political life increasingly took on sectarian character-

istics. The dominance of sectarian leaders—in part as a consequence of their political influence—was all encompassing, spanning, political, social, economic, and legal, enforced by violent militias (Saouli, 2019). Unsurprisingly, in such conditions of dominance, corruption was rife and bureaucracies inert.

The Ta'if Accords ended the Lebanese civil war by building on the National Pact of 1943, enshrining sectarian difference in the fabric of the state. In particular, leaders of wartime militias retained positions of prominence in the post-war landscape. In the years that followed, elites captured state resources and distributed them across their constituencies through clientelist networks that undermined state building efforts in pursuit of group and self interest. This landscape “trapped” Lebanese politics in a form of “zombie power sharing” (Nagle, 2020; Makdisi and Marktaner, 2009).

In Iraq, following the 2003 US led invasion which toppled Saddam Hussein, the establishment of the *muhassassa* system of government by the coalition provisional authority attempted to capture ethno-sectarian demographics within the formal political system. This elite bargain allocated positions of influence on the grounds of ethnicity and sect, incentivizing elite engagement with government actions. In this landscape, government formation was forged by grant elite bargains, sacrificing political interest in the process (Dodge and Mansour, 2020).

The architects of power sharing agreements in Lebanon and Iraq created a landscape beset by paradox: political stability was ensured by balancing the interest of communal elite against the broader collective (Cammett and Issar, 2010). Communal elites were able to accrue vast fortunes through capitalizing

on their positions of influence and a lack of oversight (Salloukh, 2019). In this context, elite interest trumped national interest, with hollowed out states unable to fulfil obligations to their citizenry (Nucho, 2016; Cammett, 2014).

In both Lebanon and Iraq, the nature of power-sharing created political landscapes that bred corruption and elite self-interest. Resentment quickly grew between communal groups, reinforcing lines of exclusion in the process. But the corruption of elites meant that resentment also began to ferment against those in positions of power. In recent years, anger at the sectarian domination of political systems has erupted in protest yet it was 2019 that marked the most serious challenge to the power-sharing system.

Across the final months of 2019, this simmering anger erupted as protesters took to the streets of Lebanon and Iraq. Calls for political, economic, and social reform rang out amidst mass mobilizations that prompted the prime ministers of both states to resign. Though protesters were met with violence by militias associated with sectarian elites, protesters were determined to continue on their path to reform.

Understanding Discontent

Seeking to better capture the nature of this frustration, a joint SEPAD-TOI project put a survey into the field to capture the feelings of people across both states. The results point to a deep-seated anger at the ways in which politics is ordered, capturing anger at socio-economic conditions, government performance, and the actions of officials.

In Lebanon, respondents painted a bleak picture. When asked about the most important

national issues, security and stability were cited as issues of most serious concern, closely followed by fighting poverty and unemployment. Locally, fighting poverty and unemployment were deemed more important, emblematic of the devastating socio-economic crisis endured by the Lebanese state at the time. Few believed that they had support from the state. When asked who they would turn to in the case of serious economic challenges, 48.8% stated that they would turn to their family while 38.2% said they would manage on their own. In contrast, the government was viewed as a source of support by only 5.2% of respondents. Moreover, 80% of respondents were not at all satisfied with government performance, while 88.4% disagreed or strongly disagreed with the statement that public officials in Lebanon provide services to citizens without expecting anything in return.

In such conditions, tensions between rich and poor, and between government and opposition supporters were held to be most significant, with 50.8% of respondents viewing tensions between rich and poor as a big or moderate problem, and 53.5% of respondents viewing tensions between government and opposition supporters as a big or moderate problem. In contrast, sectarian divisions were deemed not a problem by 53.1% of respondents, and tensions between Christian and Muslim were deemed not a problem by 61.6% of respondents.

In Iraq, a similar picture was revealed. At a national level, poverty and unemployment were deemed the most pressing issues, closely followed by maintaining security and stability. Much like in Lebanon, the day-to-day dimensions of socio-economic crises featured centrally in the minds of people. Only 1.2% believed that addressing sectarian tensions was the most important, whilst there was a

broad anger at entrenched sectarian elites. Locally, such issues were equally prevalent, with 41.2% of respondents believing that addressing unemployment and fighting poverty were most important. Only 2.6% of respondents viewed reducing sectarian tensions as the most important issue.

Few respondents believed that they had support from the government, with 42.7% of respondents suggesting that they would turn to their family for support. Anger at government performance was widespread: 43.5% of respondents were not at all satisfied with government performance with a further 20% not satisfied. Unsurprisingly, this anger manifested in tensions between government and opposition supporters. An overwhelming majority of 64.7% of respondents described tensions between government and opposition supporters as a problem, while similar sentiments were found when asked about tensions between rich and poor.

Elections

In an effort to take the sting out of the protests, elections were declared in both states. Protest movements in Lebanon and Iraq sought to field candidates who reflected the ideas of the movements, albeit to varying degrees of success as a result of the heterogeneous opinions at play. The elections returned surprising results. Despite the anger at sectarian parties expressed by protesters in Lebanon and Iraq—as reflected in their slogan “all of them means all of them”—protester candidates failed to match the hopes of many. These results beg the question: why did anti-sectarian protesters vote for sectarian parties?

In Iraq, elections returned Mustafa al-Sadr’s faction with 73 seats, the largest single bloc

in parliament, dramatically changing the balance of power within the elite pact, albeit not in the way that protesters wanted. The Sadrists articulated a broadly nationalist position, setting the group apart from other Shi'a parties who possessed links with Iran. With a turnout of just 36%, the elections were characterized by widespread discontent and while the Fateh Alliance—with links to both Iran and certain parts of the Popular Mobilization Forces—lost a large number of seats, the dominance of erstwhile members of the elite, notably the Sadrist movement, was clear. *Imtidad*, a party that emerged from the Tishreen movement, was able to secure 9 seats whilst most other parties associated with Tishreen boycotted the elections. The elections reveal a tension between the status quo parties and those emerging from the protests.

In Lebanon, over 80% of parliamentary seats were won by parties and candidates associated with the establishment. Structural factors pertaining to electoral spending, restrictive voting procedures and the lack of a viable electoral oversight body were all important issues, but the palpable fear of violence continued to play a part. While the main political parties emerged from elections largely intact, the Christian Free Patriotic Movement lost seats, becoming the second largest Christian party behind the Lebanese Forces.

Central to responses in both Lebanon and Iraq were fears about safety and security. Such concerns were hardly surprising, encapsulating broad worries about violence, militias, and more human security concerns around socio-economic issues, access to food, fuel, healthcare, and shelter. Lebanon continues to endure a harrowing economic crisis while the Iraqi state has experienced similar types of challenges. Concerns about safety and security are central in understanding

why anti-sectarian protesters voted for sectarian candidates. While the protests demonstrated the ability to imagine political life free from the shackles of sectarianism, the material realities of daily life suggests that material support remains a key mechanism in the arsenal of sectarian leaders.

Conclusions

Whilst it is too soon to assess the enduring success or failure of the 2019 protests, the process of transformation is clearly underway. The protests demonstrate that it is possible to imagine a form of politics free from the dominance of sectarianism, but the realities of implementing such a system are far harder. Untangling the material realities of a political system based on and reinforced by sectarian identities is one that will take time and effort as a result of the enduring legacy of sectarianism as an ordering principle in both states. Processes of desectarianization are long, complex journeys and while it appears that both Lebanon and Iraq have embarked on these journeys, they remain in the formative stages. ♦

References

- Cammett, Melani and Sukriti Issar, 2010. "Bricks and Mortar Clientelism: Sectarianism and the Logics of Welfare Allocation in Lebanon." *World Politics* 62:3 381-421
- Cammett, Melani. 2014. *Compassionate Communalism: Welfare and Sectarianism in Lebanon*, Ithaca, New York: Cornell University Press
- Dodge, Toby. 2018. "Bourdieu goes to Baghdad; explaining hybrid political identities in Iraq." *Journal of Historical Sociology* 31:1 25-38.

Mabon, Simon. 2020. "Four Questions about Desectarianization." *Review of Faith and International Affairs*, 18:1 1-11.

Makdisi, Samir and Marcus Marktanner. 2009. "Trapped by Consociationism: The Case of Lebanon." *Topics in Middle Eastern and African Economies* 11.

Nagle, John. 2020. "Consociationalism is Dead! Long Live Zombie Power-Sharing." *Studies in Ethnicity and Nationalism* 20:2 137-144.

Nucho, Joanne Rand. 2016. *Everyday Sectarianism in Urban Lebanon: Infrastructures, Public Services and Power*, Princeton University Press.

Salloukh, Bassel, Rabie Barakat, Jinan S Al-Habbal, Lara. W Khattab, and Shoghig Mikaelian. 2015. *The Politics of Sectarianism in Postwar Lebanon*. London: Pluto Press.

_____. 2019. "Taif and the Lebanese State: The Political Economy of a Very Sectarian Public Sector." *Nationalism and Ethnic Politics* 25:1 (2019) 43-60.

Salloukh, Bassel. 2020. "Consociational Power-Sharing in the Arab World: A Critical Stocktaking." *Studies in Ethnicity and Nationalism* 20:2 100-108.

Saouli, Adham. 2019. "Sectarianism and political order in Iraq and Lebanon." *Studies in Ethnicity and Nationalism*, 19:1.